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тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

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акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

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дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

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Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxamatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
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MATLUBOV Mansur Muratovich
DSc, professor
KHUDOYBERDIEVA Gulrukh Sobirjonovna
Assistant
Samarkand State Medical University

POSTNATAL ADAPTATION PERIOD OF NEWBORNS WHO ARE BORN TO MOTHERS WITH PRE-ECLAMPSIA USING VARIOUS SEDATIVES

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ABSTRACT

Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy is a serious problem that can lead to various complications for the mother and fetus such as premature delivery, delayed growth and development of the fetus, placental insufficiency, eclampsia and even death of the mother or child. Due to the fact that during pre-eclampsia leading clinical manifestations are the formation of arterial hypertension, edema-proteinuric syndrome, total spasm of the peripheral vessels, leading eventually to gross violations of major life support systems. As the gestational age increases, a number of pathological changes occur in the cardiorespiratory system, up to the development of heart failure. Therefore, the development of anesthetic protocols and guidelines specifically adapted to this group of patients is very important to prevent adverse effects.

Key words: pregnant women, preeclampsia, arterial hypertension, edema, proteinuria, sedation.

МАТЛУБОВ Мансур Муратович
Д.м.н., профессор
ХУДОЙБЕРДИЕВА Гулрух Собиржонова
Ассистент
Самаркандский Государственный Медицинский Университет

ПОСТНАТАЛЬНЫЙ АДАПТАЦИОННЫЙ ПЕРИОД НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ, РОДИВШИХСЯ ОТ МАТЕРЕЙ С ПРЕЭКЛАМПСИЕЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ СЕДАТИВНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Гипертензивные нарушения в период беременности - это серьезная проблема, которая может привести к различным осложнениям для матери и плода такие как преждевременные роды,

задержка роста и развития плода, плацентарную недостаточность, эклампсию и даже гибель матери или ребенка. В связи с тем, что во время преэклампсии ведущими клиническими проявлениями являются формирование артериальной гипертензии, отечно-протеинурического синдрома, тотального спазма периферических сосудов, приводящих в конечном итоге к грубым нарушениям основных систем жизнеобеспечения. По мере увеличения сроков гестации происходит ряд патологических изменений со стороны кардиореспираторной системы, вплоть до развития сердечной недостаточности. Поэтому разработка анестезиологических протоколов и руководств, специально адаптированных для этой группы пациентов, очень важна для предотвращения негативных последствий.

Ключевые слова: спинальная анестезия, кесарево сечения, беременные, преэклампсия, артериальная гипертензия, отёки, протеинурия, седация, новорожденные, плод

MATLUBOV Mansur Muratovich
t.f.d. professor
XUDOYBERDIEVA Gulrux Sobirjonovna
Assistent
Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti

TURLI SEDATIV DORILAR TA`SIRIDA PRIEKLAMPSYASI BOR BO`LGAN AYOLLARDAN TUG`ILGAN CHAQALOQLARNING POSTNATAL ADAPTATSYASI

IZOH

Homiladorlik davridagi gipertenziv kasalliklar ona va homila uchun erta tug'ilish, o'sish va homila rivojlanishining kechikishi, platsenta yetishmovchiligi, eklampsiya va hatto ona yoki bolaning o'limi kabi turli xil asoratlarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin bo'lgan jiddiy muammodir. Prieklampsiya paytida asosiy klinik ko'rinishlar arterial gipertenziya, shish-proteinurik sindrom, periferik tomirlarning umumiy spazmining shakllanishi bo'lib, natijada hayotni qo'llab-quvvatlashning asosiy tizimlarining buzilishiga olib keladi. Homiladorlik davri oshgani sayin, yurak yetishmovchiligining rivojlanishiga qadar kardiorespirator tizimda bir qator patologik o'zgarishlar sodir bo'ladi. Shu sababli, ushbu bemorlar guruhi uchun maxsus moslashtirilgan anestetik protokollar va ko'rsatmalarni ishlab chiqish salbiy oqibatlarining oldini olish uchun juda muhim bo'lib hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: homilador ayollar, prieklampsiya, arterial gipertenziya, shish, proteinuriya, sedatsiya.

Relevance: A distinctive feature of modern obstetrics is the steady increase in operative delivery in order to improve pregnancy outcomes for both mother and newborn. Preeclampsia complicates up to 8% of pregnancies and is a leading cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide [1]. In these conditions, the choice of anesthesia is of great importance. There are special requirements for anesthesiological care in obstetrics: it is necessary to protect the mother's body from surgical trauma and at the same time to prevent negative effects on the fetus, to preserve as much as possible its adaptive-regulatory mechanisms responsible for postnatal adaptation [2]. It is known that the leading clinical manifestations of preeclampsia are the formation of arterial hypertension, edematous-proteinuric syndrome, total spasm of peripheral vessels, ultimately leading to gross violations of the main life support systems.

Purpose of the study: To study in a comparative aspect the features of the course of the postnatal period of adaptation of newborns born to women with preeclampsia under the conditions of the use of various sedatives during caesarean section and spinal anesthesia. Material and methods: A prospective comparative randomized longitudinal study was conducted in the regional perinatal center of Samarkand. The study included 40 newborns born to pregnant women with moderate preeclampsia who were delivered by elective cesarean section. Exclusion criteria were: refusal to participate in the study, multiple pregnancies, concomitant pathology in the acute stage or decompensation, the presence of contraindications to spinal anesthesia.

The diagnosis of moderate preeclampsia was established in the presence of arterial hypertension (BP) $\geq 140/90$ mm Hg. in combination with other unfavorable conditions: proteinuria ≥ 3 g/l; increased creatinine levels; oliguria; thrombocytopenia; increased levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALAT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST); pain in the epigastrium, right hypochondrium; intrauterine growth retardation [4]. All pregnant women initially received magnesium, antihypertensive therapy, and prevention of fetal respiratory distress syndrome [5]. The patients of the presented groups had no differences in terms of delivery time, obstetric history, the presence of chronic fetoplacental insufficiency (CPI), NMPK, age, anthropometric data, details of the operation, and time of fetal extraction. For premedication, all women were given diphenhydramine (0.2 mg/kg) and atropine 0.5 mg. Depending on the method of anesthesia provided to mothers, all newborns were divided into 2 groups. In group I newborns (n = 22), mothers were sedated with ketamine (1 mg/kg). Puncture of the subarachnoid space was performed at the level LII–LIV using Pencil-Point G 25–26 needles in a lateral position. A hyperbaric solution of 0.5% bupivacaine solution (Longocaine-Heavy Yuria-Pharm (Ukraine)) with a solution density of 1.026 was slowly (over 1 min) injected. The anesthetic dose for SA was calculated in accordance with the proposed dosage for women in both groups [3]. In group II (n = 18) of newborns, starting from the moment of premedication, 0.5 mcg/kg dexmedetomidine (Quanadex, Yuria Pharm) was intravenously administered as a sedative for 15 minutes, the maintenance dose of which was 0.5– 0.8 mcg/kg/h throughout the entire operation until its completion. The technique and drugs for spinal anesthesia were carried out as in the previous 1st group of women. To assess newborns, the Apgar score was used at 1 and 5 minutes of life and the NACS score at 1 hour and 24 hours after birth. The course of early postnatal adaptation of newborns was assessed using cardiointervalography immediately after birth and 24 hours later. Carrying out a mathematical analysis of the heart rhythm of newborns, in addition to the generally accepted indicators - Mo, AMo, ΔX , IN, the coefficient of pharmacological discoordination (PDC) was calculated. Adaptation was assessed using the classification of R.M. Baevsky, according to which four levels were identified: satisfactory, unsatisfactory, tension and breakdown. We also studied morphometric parameters, the degree of asphyxia and the need for resuscitation measures, and the presence of fetal growth restriction syndrome (FGR). The concentration of glucose and total cortisol in the umbilical cord blood of newborns was also studied (radioimmune method). Statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using the Statistica 7.0 application package (StatSoft Inc., USA). Qualitative characteristics are described by simply indicating the quantity and percentage for each category. All quantitative characteristics were tested for compliance with their normal distribution using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Differences between the compared values were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion: Children born to mothers of both groups did not have statistically significant differences in gestational age, physical development parameters, and frequency of development of FGR. It should be noted the high proportion of premature babies: 82.8% of mothers of the 1st group and 89.3% of newborns of mothers of the 2nd group had a gestation period of less than 37 weeks, on average 32-33 weeks. More than 60% of children had FGR with the same frequency in both groups ($p=0.25$)

Table 1.

Clinical characteristics of children at birth

Index	Group 1 (n=22)	Group 2 (n=18)	P
Gestational age, weeks	33 (31; 35)	32 (31; 34)	0,24
Body weight at birth, g	1787,27 \pm 86,13	1808,06 \pm 10,51	0,83
Weight <2500 g	18	12	0,64
Weight <1500 g	3	2	0,17
Body length at birth, cm	41,66 \pm 0,66	40,37 \pm 0,27	0,44
FGR total, abs., %	13	10	1,2
Moderate to moderate asphyxia (P21.1)	17	9	0,6
Severe asphyxia (P21.0)	4	1	0,4
Respiratory support requirement, total	14	6	1,6

Need for mask ventilation	10	4	0,84
Need for invasive ventilation	4	2	0,5

In newborns of the compared groups, 45.5% of children born to patients in group 1 had less than 7 points on the Apgar scale at birth, and 16.7% - in group 2 ($p = 0.32$). The probability of having children with a low Apgar score (less than 7 points) from mothers with preeclampsia is higher among mothers of group 1 than among mothers of group 2, without a statistically significant difference. Asphyxia of moderate and moderate severity (Apgar score at 1 minute 4-7 points) was noted in 77.3% of children born to mothers of the 1st group under conditions of SA sedation with ketamine, and in 9 (50%) — Group 2 under SA sedation with dexmedetomidine (see Table 1). Our previously published research results showed that abdominal delivery of patients with preeclampsia using dexmedetomidine was accompanied by greater hemodynamic stability than using ketamine at all stages of the operation, especially at the perinatal stage (before fetal extraction).

Table 2.

Comparative analysis of Apgar scores

Index	Group 1 (n=22)	Group 2 (n=18)	P
Apgar score, Me [QI; QIII]			
in the 1st minute	5 [4; 6] **	7 [7; 8] **	0,28
at the 5th minute	6[5; 7]	8 [8; 9] **	
Number of newborns with Apgar score \geq 7 points, abs. (%)			
in the 1st minute of life	12 (54,5)	15 (83,3)	0,32
at 5 minutes of life	20 (80)	18 (100)	

Table 3.

Comparative indicators of cardiointervalography in newborns 2 hours after birth and 24 hours after birth

Data CIG	Group 1 (n=22)		Group 2 (n=18)		P
	2 hours after birth	24 hours after birth	2 hours after birth	24 hours after birth	
Variation range, ΔX , sec	0,084±0,004	0,087±0,002	0,088±0,015	0,094±0,006* Δ	0,05
Moda, Mo, sec.	0,30±0,005	0,41±0,006* Δ	0,39±0,006	0,46±0,006* Δ	0,05
Moda`s amplitude, MoA, %	22,06±1,4	44,46±1,04* Δ	25,09±0,98	41,8±1,3* Δ	0,05
Voltage index, IN	323,6±26,34	1252,2±45,0* Δ	442,77±94,5	889,8±31,6* Δ	0,05
КФД, усл.ед.	5,18±0,16	8,8±0,21* Δ	5,11±0,12	8,6±0,14* Δ	

Note: * - statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between groups 1 and 2; Δ - statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) relative to the previous stage of the study.

As you can see, the parameters characterizing the autonomic regulation of heart rate 2 hours after birth in newborns extracted under conditions of ketamine use (group 1) showed a significantly more pronounced activation of parasympathetic influences than in children of group 2 ($\Delta X - 0.084 + 0.004$ s ; $p < 0.05$), activity of the sympathetic regulation link (AMo - 22.06±1.4; $p < 0.05$), degree of tension in heart rate regulation (IN - 323.6±26.34 conventional units; $p < 0.05$), as well as the predominance of the intrasystemic circuit of heart rate regulation over the autonomous one, which clearly demonstrated the insignificant drug load, more frequent disruption of the restoration of spontaneous breathing, and the need for emergency sanitation of the upper respiratory tract (see Table 3).

Meanwhile, the newborns of the 2nd group were not much different from those of children born through the vaginal birth canal. The difference was a significantly more pronounced activity of the humoral channel of autonomic regulation (Mo - 0.39±0.006 s) and a lower degree of tension in the regulatory systems of the heart rhythm (IN - 442.77±94.5 conventional units). At the same time, they completely maintained the balance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions of

the ANS. There was moderate functional tension in both the intrasystemic and autonomous circuits of heart rate regulation. The FDC in children of the 1st and 2nd groups was 5.18 ± 0.16 and 5.11 ± 0.12 conventional units, which clearly characterized the minimum drug load in both groups.

24 hours after birth, children of group 1 still retained a predominance in the vegetative balance of the tone of its sympathetic department (IN - 1252.2 ± 45.0 conventional units; $p < 0.05$) with a parallel and significant increase in parasympathetic influences ($M_o - 0.41 \pm 0.006$ s, $\Delta X - 0.087 \pm 0.002$ s ($p < 0.05$)).

However, the physiological balance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic parts of the ANS, as well as the intrasystemic and autonomous circuits of heart rate regulation was completely restored within 72 hours.

24 hours after birth, a significant decrease in sympathetic influences and restoration of balance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions of the ANS was recorded in children of the 2nd group (see Table 3). At the same time, we did not register any significant differences in the studied cardiointervalography parameters in children of the 2nd group. The absolute values of SI did not go beyond the boundaries of the “stress norm”. At the same time, there was a significant difference in the studied indicators of cardiointervolography (see Table 4). The absolute values of SI were 889.8 ± 31.6 conventional units, which was an indicator of insignificant tension in the regulatory systems of the heart rhythm (but not beyond the boundaries of the “stress norm”).

Table 4.

Comparative analysis of glucose in umbilical cord blood, as well as the concentration of total cortisol in newborns

Data	Group 1 (n=22)		Group 2 (n=18)		P
	5 minutes after birth	2 hours after birth	5 minutes after birth	2 hours after birth	
Glucose mmol/l	$4,2 \pm 1,2$	$5,7 \pm 1,4^*$	$5,6 \pm 2,4$	$5,6 \pm 1,2^*$	0,01
Total cortisol (TC), nmol/l	$374,4 \pm 71,4$	$569,4 \pm 88,4^*$	$463,9 \pm 62,2$	$686,1 \pm 44,8^*$	0,01

Note: * - significance of differences ($p < 0.05$) between groups 1 and 2.

As can be seen from Table 5, in newborns extracted under conditions of ketamine use (group 1), the total cortisol at birth (at the 5th minute) was 377.4 ± 71.4 nmol/l, while in newborns extracted under conditions using dexmedetomidine as a sedative (group 2) it was 487.9 ± 68.7 nmol/l ($p < 0.01$). It should be noted that a fairly high concentration of cortisol in the blood of newborns 2 hours after birth indicated the formation of an adequate physiological response to the birth process (see Table 4). At the same time, the relatively low concentration of cortisol recorded in newborns of group 1 indicated a depression in the functional state of the sympathoadrenal system. At the same time after birth (5 minutes after birth), as in children of the 1st group, so in the children of the 2nd group, glycemia indicators did not go beyond their physiological parameters (see Table 4). However, there was a significant difference in the studied groups, which, in our opinion, is a consequence of the depressive effect of ketamine on the fetus (see Table 4).

Thus, our study, which included a comprehensive assessment of the condition of the fetus and the course of the early postnatal period, allows us to conclude that during abdominal delivery of pregnant women with preeclampsia, the method of sedative provision with dexmedetomidine does not have a statistically significant effect on the course of the period of early adaptation of newborns and the formation of the main pathological conditions.

Conclusions:

1. For pain relief during abdominal delivery, it is preferable to use spinal anesthesia due to the low risk of complications in the mother.
2. The results obtained allow us to reasonably recommend the drug dexmedetomidine as the main sedative drug from the standpoint of safety for the fetus and newborn.

3. The increased risk of adverse outcomes in children born to mothers with preeclampsia requires special attention from a neonatologist and readiness to provide respiratory support in the delivery room and intensive care, regardless of the method of anesthesia.

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Информация об авторах

Матлубов Мансур Муратович – д.м.н. профессор, заведующий кафедрой анестезиологии, реанимации и неотложной медицины. Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail:mansur.matlubov@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8596-1430>

Худойбердиева Гулрух Собиржоновна – Ассистент кафедры Анестезиологии, реанимации и неотложной медицины. Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail:xudoyberdievagulruh@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7385-363X>

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Information about the authors:

Matlubov Mansur Muratovich – Doctor of Medical Sciences Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Anesthesiology, Reanimation and Emergency Medicine. Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. (hidden) <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8596-1430>

Khudoiberdieva Gulrukh Sobirjonovna – Assistant of the Department of Anesthesiology, Reanimation and Emergency Medicine. Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. (hidden) <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7385-363X>

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Matlubov M.M. – ideological concept of work, text writing; article editing;

Khudoiberdieva G.S. – collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

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ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
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Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000